

A TEXTILE-BASED TISSUE OXYGENATION SENSOR USING MULTI-WAVELENGTH NEAR-INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

Sensawear is a University of Bern-spinoff collaborating with OST Buchs to commercialize near-infrared electronics to power a wearable, textile-based sensor for continuous tissue oxygenation (StO₂) monitoring for the prevention of pressure injuries developed during a SNF/Innosuisse Bridge Discovery grant. The inherently-low emission power of a textile-based sensor requires high-output light sources and highly-sensitive photo detectors, while the use as a continuous monitor in healthcare requires low noise, repeatability, safety, and ease-of-use. The collaborative work has resulted in a functional demonstrator soon to be used for pilot studies, with measurement quality comparable to industry standard devices used for research purposes.

KEYWORDS: near-infrared spectroscopy, medical device, continuous monitoring, wearable technology

INTRODUCTION

Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) has been developed in the field of medicine as a safe, non-invasive means of resolving physiological changes based primarily on the concentrations of the biological chromophores hemoglobin (HbO) and deoxy-hemoglobin (HHb). NIRS can resolved changes in HbO and HHb concentrations by using light in the NIR range between 670 nm and 990 nm. The development of NIRS over the past several decades has seen great improvements in precision, penetration depth, repeatability and success in clinical applications such as functional brain oximetry. However, a key field has been left relatively undeveloped; the field of wearable deep-tissue oxygenation monitoring. With millions of people developing painful and potentially fatal pressure injuries each year – injuries which result from poor StO₂ due to a lack of proper movement – a technology to continuously, comfortably, and non-invasively monitor StO₂ is perfectly suited to prevent such injuries and many others which occur as a result of poor StO₂.

This unmet clinical need was the motivation of the Bridge Discovery grant which funded the ProTex research project in 2019 led by the University of Bern together with Empa St. Gallen and OST in Buchs to develop the world's first thin, wearable, comfortable NIRS sensors with no hard components that could continuously monitor StO₂ without introducing pressure points. A key component, the hardware unit itself, was developed by teams at two institutes at OST; the electronics institute ESA led by Prof. Piai and the photonics group of the institute IMP led by Prof. Markus Michler.

CONCEPT

A hardware unit needed to be designed and built specifically for the integration with newly development textile-based NIRS sensors. The NIRS measurement modality chosen was continuous wave NIRS (CW-NIRS) which measures light intensity as a function of distance traveled through tissue and calculates changes in chromophore concentration using the modified Beer-Lambert Law (MBLL). This unit needed to be modular to accommodate interchangeable optics components such as LED light sources and APD/PD light detectors based on sensor performance to keep the system adaptable. The limiting range of StO₂ detectability was numerically and experimentally examined by Cantieni et al. [1]. The unit needed to be safe and relatively compact for use in clinical environments, while interfacing easily with standard laptops to allow the team at the University of Bern to control the parameters of the hardware unit and do on-the-fly post-processing of raw data to calculate and plot physiological data in real time. The sensors required a low-loss interface to the optical components embedded in the hardware unit to ensure low-noise, repeatable measurements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The hardware unit, developed under the working title of ResearchBox by OST, is capable of sampling 32 optical channels at a sampling rate of 100 Hz to accommodate the most complex of the sensors designed by UniBern. This sensor uses four emission points and eight detection points with spacing and geometry optimized by a genetic algorithm to achieve the highest spatial resolution and penetration depth with the minimum optical channels and number of wavelengths.

The ResearchBox (Fig. 1) uses high-powered LEDs as light sources and transmits light via optical fibers to the sensors in four different NIRS wavelengths, also optimized for increased StO₂ reconstruction.

High tissue penetration depth and good resolution of changes in chromophore concentration require low SNR, thus highly sensitive APDs are used to collect light from the sensor.

The electronics comprise a processor board, amplifier board, detection board and source board, all custom designed by OST. The LEDs in the source board are interfaced directly to the sensors' fiber optics via SMA connectors such that the fiber bundle makes direct contact with each LED over an optimized region of near-zero-gradient optical power transmission.

Because human tissue is highly scattering and the fluence of back-reflected light drops off quickly with distance from the point of light injection, the hardware unit was designed to resolve the detected light with a high dynamic range. This allows good SNR at long measurement distances while avoiding APD saturation at short distances. This was done using a 24-bit ADC with 8-channels allowing simultaneous sampling together with logarithmic amplifiers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial testing of the ResearchBox when connected to the ProTex textile-based NIRS sensors showed strong performance over the measurement distances required for deep StO₂ monitoring. The high sampling rate allowed clean filtering while retaining near real-time monitoring of changes in StO₂. The ResearchBox's ambient light filtering algorithm kept signals constant regardless of environment, and thermal drift during measurement periods was minimal thanks to a cooling fan. Measurements of changes in StO₂ were precise and repeatable, with high accuracy when compared to an industry standard frequency-domain NIRS device.

CONCLUSIONS

The successful development of the ResearchBox is a vital step on the road to commercialization for Sensawear. The fundamental design will allow for collection of clinical feasibility data and serves as the groundwork for further miniaturization, cost reduction, and compliance to ISO 13485 for a fast market entry as a CE-certified, class II medical device.

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REFERENCES

[1] T. Cantieni et al., "Detectability of Low-Oxygenated Regions in Human Muscle Tissue Using Near-Infrared Spectroscopy and Phantom Models", *Biomedical Optics Express*, DOI 10.1364/BOE.473563, 2022.

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